

On what basis to award public contracts

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Policy recommendations

1. **Reduce reliance on lowest price:** Gradually make the application of best price-quality ratio for European tenders less optional and subsequently move more towards sustainable public procurement, to reduce the predominant reliance on lowest price procurement.
2. **Promote the inclusion of quality and sustainability in supplier selection decisions across various solutions:** Focus policies that advocate for integrating quality and sustainability into supplier selection decisions not only on award criteria, but also across other solutions, including standards, certifications, and alternative procurement models like renting or buying as a service.
3. **Differentiate award criteria in three factors:** Clearly delineate price, quality, and sustainability as three distinct factors for awarding public contracts rather than solely focusing on price and quality. Avoid subsuming sustainability under quality to make sustainability more prominent.
4. **Train procurement staff:** Provide comprehensive training and education programs aimed at developing effective supplier selection models.
5. **Enhance measurement of tenders and actual contract realization:** Place greater emphasis on measuring quality and sustainability in both tender announcements and reporting on actual contract outcomes. The current focus on tender process elements and contract value is insufficient for evaluating the overall effectiveness of public procurement.

1. Introduction

Every year, over 250,000 public authorities in the EU spend around €2 to 2,5 trillion per year (on average about 14 to 15% of GDP) on the public procurement of services, works, and supplies. Energy usage and mineral usage likely reflect similar percentages (Steenmeijer et al., 2021). Ensuring that this taxpayer money is spent efficiently, effectively, and

sustainably is of common European interest (EC, 2017).

EU public procurement legislation requires all public contracts above certain thresholds to be put out for tender respecting principles such as transparency, equal treatment, non-discrimination, and proportionality. The current rules encourage authorities, rather than to award contracts on the basis of lowest price (i.e., price), to also integrate qualitative award criteria (i.e., quality) and criteria

related to sustainable and socially inclusive approaches (i.e., sustainability) (EC, 2017).

While the European Commission assists contracting authorities to consider quality and sustainability for awarding contracts as well, this is not common practice. Awarding contracts on the basis of lowest price only is the most popular method for awarding contracts in European tenders, accounting for an average of 52% in 2022. There are also significant variations between member states in how often they apply lowest price only, suggesting room for improvement (see Figure 1). Moreover, we also see that Sustainable Public Procurement (SPP) is a challenge in many member states, as we illustrated in one of our earlier policy briefs (Nicolas et al., 2024).

Figure 1: Extent to which lowest price is used throughout Europe in 2022, based on Tender Electronics Daily (TED) data

In this policy brief, we explain the advantages and disadvantages of supplier selection models that include price only (lowest price), price and quality (Best Price-Quality Ratio; BPQR) or price, quality, and sustainability (SPP). We do this based on a brief history of supplier selection in the public domain in the EU. Additionally, we elaborate on five policy

recommendations that could contribute to finding a better balance between lowest price tenders and tenders that also consider quality and sustainability for supplier selection decisions.

2. Public procurement from the 19th century: a growing number of lowest price tenders

In the early days of public governance, there were not yet any tender regulations, and public procurement rarely involved a tender procedure. If it did, it was typically a kind of price auction. Varied by member state, but not until (or as early as) around the 19th century did public procurement become a more serious field of study in many EU member states, with the first small steps toward modern tender legislations.

The focus on lowest price back in the days did not mean that quality was considered irrelevant. Buyers attempted to guarantee minimum quality by establishing requirements. Sometimes there were social requirements as well, such as workdays of no more than 10 hours for specific government contracts (Hamilton, 2022; Richardson, 1897). Lowest price tenders also have merits worth considering:

- It encourages lower initial procurement costs, and if those costs are not raised later, low procurement costs provide public value (see also Decarolis, 2014).
- It is faster and easier to advertise and award, making tenders more accessible for less experienced or smaller suppliers.
- There are fewer opportunities for corruption, cronyism, collusion (Baranek and Titl, 2020; Titl and Geys, 2019; Titl et al., 2021), and biased decision-making

(Kahneman, 2021) as minimum quality requirements are prescribed, and no qualitative assessment of quality is involved.

However, there turned out to be multiple drawbacks to lowest-price-based procurement as well:

- Purchasing based solely on the lowest price puts strong pressure on price alone (see also Figure 2). The only lever that suppliers can pull to distinguish themselves is price. When a buyer awards contracts based solely on price, it fails to reward suppliers who offer higher quality than the minimum requirements or innovative solutions for a (somewhat) higher price. It will also increase the risk of suppliers offering a price that is unrealistically low, which is difficult for buyers to prove during the tender phase.
- For a lowest price contract, the buyer must define the specifications. It can be difficult for government buyers, who navigate thousands of markets, to have enough expertise to draft good specifications. Also, certain specifications can artificially narrow markets. And if errors are made in technical specifications, the buyer is responsible.
- Suppliers also have an incentive not to report any errors in the specifications during tender procedures and then seek to remedy those mistakes through surcharges after being awarded the contract. The low initial procurement costs are then nullified. While buyers can usually impose fines, this is not always done. Suppliers are aware of this and can anticipate it.

Figure 2: Procurement based on the lowest price

Lowest price incentivizes suppliers to barely meet, or even undercut, the requirements while minimizing costs. Suppliers who excel in this approach are rewarded by winning more contracts and earning higher profits. This pushes fair and high-quality suppliers out of the market and undermines buyers' trust in the marketplace in the long term.

3. Public procurement from the '70s: a growing awareness of the benefits of best price-quality ratio tenders

In 1971, the first European directives regarding public procurement were published. These directives explicitly stated that awarding contracts does not have to be done based on the lowest price alone, but that quality *could* also be taken into account, in addition to what is minimally required. Examples of such quality related criteria are technical merit, aesthetic and functional characteristics, or an implementation plan.

Despite the explicit possibilities afforded by the law and efforts to induce contracting authorities to base more of their purchasing decisions on both price and quality, this practice is not yet widespread in all sectors or all member states (see Figure 1). And in cases where contracts are awarded based on both price and quality, quality often still has a low weight, or suppliers find it challenging to differentiate themselves based on overly general award criteria.

This focus on price is also reflected in the European tender forms that contracting authorities use to announce that a government contract is open to competition or has been awarded. The contract value is a required field (regularly filled in incorrectly), but buyers are not required to include the scores for qualitative award criteria. Even just the names of the qualitative award criteria are often not mentioned.

There are interesting examples of member states that have managed to change their focus on lowest price. For instance, in the Netherlands, from 1 April 2013, it became compulsory to base contract awards on BPQR, unless there is a good reason to apply lowest price. The percentage of tenders for major construction and infrastructure contracts awarded based on lowest price decreased from 70% in 2008 to 22% in 2021.

It is possible that the Dutch merely jumped aboard a trend that was already in motion. However, when we look at Germany, for example, we can see that the number of tenders awarded based on lowest price is increasing in the same period. The percentage of lowest-price tenders for large construction and infrastructure contracts in Germany has increased from 50% in 2008 to 94% in 2021.

BPQR is not only used relatively often in the Netherlands but also in countries such as France, Norway, Ireland, and Denmark. The use of BPQR in these countries has demonstrated the following benefits of BPQR:

- BPQR creates an extra “quality lever” that suppliers can “pull” to set themselves apart from the rest (see also see Figure 3). There is pressure to offer low prices and high quality. Buyers now have the option to select suppliers based on both price and quality, creating pressure to keep prices

low and quality high. This allows suppliers offering better quality, albeit at a slightly higher price, to have a chance at winning tenders. BPQR also introduces an additional test to determine if suppliers are really up to the task at hand, as they are required to submit more than just a price quote.

- Buyers can also relax specific technical requirements that only a small portion of the market can meet and turn them into award criteria, possibly in combination with functional requirements. This opens up opportunities for suppliers who could not meet the original technical requirement, and it allows for alternative or innovative solutions to be considered.

Figure 3: Procurement based on price and quality related criteria

However, drawbacks have also become apparent:

- Firstly, the benefits of lowest price naturally do not apply to BPQR tenders. Organizing a BPQR tender is more complex, with higher risks of corruption, and the initial purchase price may be higher on average. In addition, public officers often feel rewarded for avoiding visible issues and choosing the safe road. They are less often rewarded for using more complex techniques for tenders, although these could, on average, have significant potential value for society. We also note that there is a higher risk of lawsuits for BPQR tenders due to subjective quality assessments, especially when the cost of litigation is low, discouraging buyers from using BPQR.

This might partly explain why lowest price is a popular method in countries such as Sweden (see Figure 1).

- While price is relatively easy for buyers to measure, assessing quality is often more challenging. Developing award criteria may not be as difficult as defining specific technical requirements, but it poses the risk of suppliers overpromising or hoping that offered quality in the bid will not be thoroughly checked. Measures such as verification processes, training bid assessors, and requesting (additional) evidence of suppliers can mitigate this risk.
- Monitoring offered quality during execution can also be more challenging than monitoring whether the minimum requirements were satisfied. Nevertheless, relevant quality related aspects will get noticed by the user, if no one else.
- Suppliers find it more difficult to submit bids considering both price and quality, leading to the emergence of bid management teams, bid writers, and consultancy firms to assist suppliers in writing bids.
- Developing a robust BPQR supplier selection model can be complex, with contracting authorities still making mistakes in supplier selection. Price often remains the determining factor, consciously or not. And buyers are often still using so-called relative scoring methods for price when using point based award methods, despite repeated warnings from lawyers, business experts and economists not to do so (Telgen and Schotanus, 2010; Schotanus et al., 2022; Manunza, 2018; Bergman and Lundberg, 2013). In addition, money-based award methods are not always applied as intended. Common mistakes include giving too little or too much value to quality.

Nevertheless, member states utilizing BPQR are learning and improving their ability to conduct purchasing based on both price and quality. They have a broader toolkit, using lowest price, highest quality or everything in between based on the procurement's nature. For instance, they can use lowest price for simple commodities delivered by small companies. Similarly, they can utilize highest quality for procurements with well-defined budgets and no or limited risks of excessive quality, such as in the procurement of public transportation or healthcare services.

Though BPQR has drawbacks, it does incentivize suppliers to excel in both price and quality, reducing underperformance and unfair competition, and keeping markets healthy. Balancing the application of lowest price and BPQR appropriately can minimize the drawbacks of each method, ensuring a fair and efficient procurement process. With the right balance, suppliers with a good price-quality ratio are rewarded by winning more contracts, thereby driving out underperforming low-cost suppliers from the market and enhancing buyers' trust in the marketplace.

4. 21st century procurement: a growing awareness of the benefits of best price-quality-sustainability ratio tenders

In recent years, organizations such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and the European Commission have promoted SPP to address societal issues. Additionally, devastating events such as COVID-19 and the conflict in Ukraine have underscored the importance of circular and environmentally friendly procurement in

reducing dependency on imports from outside of Europe.

When contracting authorities consider price and quality in their purchasing decisions, this does not necessarily translate into environmentally or socially responsible outcomes. A high-quality product may not necessarily be beneficial for the environment or for the people who made the product. Consequently, when a government focuses solely on price and quality, contracts are more likely to be awarded to suppliers with larger environmental footprints or fewer social considerations, as these suppliers may offer lower prices or higher quality under current tax and subsidy conditions.

Despite the potential benefits, the incorporation of sustainability considerations into procurement practices remains limited. While there are numerous best practices for SPP, it is not yet common practice, even in leading countries. For example, in some leading countries, certain contracting authorities opt for SPP in specific markets, which indicates that sustainable options are present, while others do not opt for SPP (Van Berkel and Schotanus, 2021; Zijp et al., 2022).

Moreover, there remains a lack of emphasis on measurement and reporting about SPP, despite advancements such as the new e-forms for TED. Buyers are however still not obligated to report whether and how they consider social and environmental factors in their procurement decisions. Current additional national systems such as MVIZET (a Dutch self-reporting tool linked to TED data) are required to measure the level of sustainability and innovativeness of tenders. And even such systems still focus on the tendering process rather than contract outcomes.

Nevertheless, incorporating sustainability into procurement – next to price and quality – can offer advantages:

- By considering price, quality, and sustainability, contracting authorities now have three levers to guide supplier selection (see Figure 4). This approach enables the inclusion of sustainable solutions and social entrepreneurs who may not have been competitive based solely on price and quality, potentially delivering greater societal value.
- Setting sustainable minimum requirements can be challenging for a buyer, even more so than for qualitative requirements. Developments are progressing rapidly, and requirements can exacerbate concerns of overly restricting the market. A simple example is when a buyer stipulates that a new viaduct must be made for 100% out of used materials. The requirement of 100% might be impossible with current technology for all or most suppliers. Suppliers may opt out or bid without fulfilling the requirement. Setting an award criterion for using used materials between 95% and 100% in the evaluation process prevents such issues.

Figure 4: Procurement based on price, quality, and sustainability related criteria (SPP)

There are also challenges associated with integrating sustainability into procurement practices, in addition to the challenges associated with quality:

- Measuring sustainability aspects are often the most challenging to verify and monitor because they tend to occur out of sight. Users cannot easily verify the working

conditions under which, for example, a product to be purchased was made. However, there are opportunities for verification and monitoring, such as requesting for certificates and evidence, and random inspections.

- Incorporating all three elements into an supplier selection model can become quite complex for many tenders. Nevertheless, simpler alternatives can be envisioned, such as setting fixed levels of price and then using a limited number (e.g. two or three) of quality and sustainability related aspects as award criteria. Other alternative methods include reserving contracts for social entrepreneurs or utilizing modern procurement models. Traditional procurement models assume the purchase of goods or works, which may not encourage reuse. However, when the supplier retains ownership (e.g., through buying as a service, leasing, renting, or sharing) or buys secondhand, the potential for reuse by the supplier increases significantly.

Similarly to the reasons outlined for BPQR, SPP provides fairer opportunities for suppliers who may not always offer the lowest prices or the highest quality but deliver the most societal value. By implementing SPP more frequently, suppliers solely driven by profit motives will secure fewer contracts, enhancing citizens' trust in government operations and, ultimately, in our democracy.

Conclusions

Considering all these considerations, how can the European Commission promote BPQR and SPP? We propose five policy recommendations:

1. Gradually make BPQR and subsequently SPP less optional to apply. The

Netherlands has demonstrated that applying a comply or explain mechanism for BPQR can effectively drive behavioral change.

2. Focus policies on promoting quality and sustainability not only on award criteria but also on standards, certifications, procurement models (e.g., leasing, renting), and reserved contracts, where applicable.
3. Explicitly differentiate between price, quality, and sustainability to make sustainability more prominent; sustainability should preferably not be a subset of quality but should be recognized for its specific (external) advantages and disadvantages.
4. Provide training and education on establishing supplier selection models. This is a specialized field, and many instances exist where these models are misapplied.
5. Place greater emphasis on measuring quality and sustainability during tenders and contract outcomes. The current focus on tender process elements is still quite traditional (e.g. with a focus on price and properties of the tender) and inadequate for assessing overall effectiveness of public procurement. Experiences with self-reporting tools as mentioned in this policy brief can serve as valuable examples.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Further Information:

Schotanus, F. (2022). A better world starts with public procurement, Inaugural address, Utrecht University, 1 July 2022. URL: <https://www.uu.nl/medewerkers/RestApi/Public/GetFile?Employee=55038&l=EN&id=1225&t=000000>

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